

Supplementary Figure 4. Covidence Tags	
Tags	Description
Awaiting classification	Default in Covidence
No discussion, no application	Authors mention, describe, discuss how to use ToxRTool, but there is no specific application of ToxRTool in the publication.
Not in English	Allows the team to identify non-English articles for translation using one or all of the following applications: Google translate, DocTranslator , DeepL . If the translation is of low and suspect quality, then the non-English article will be excluded (Table 5).
On going study	Default in Covidence
Review, Secondary discussion of ToxRTool	Authors describe other groups work, use, application, or potential application of ToxRTool; the article will likely be considered a review article.
Supplementary	The article's content is considered useful and could be used as background information but the overall article content does not fall within the project scope.
<p>Supplementary Figure 4. Covidence Tags. This table summarizes the tags created or they are default tags. Both help sort out publications that may be useful for context but will be excluded or supplementary materials.</p>	